

Controlled Frontal Polymerization and Direct Writing of Cyclooctadiene-based Inks

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Frontal Ring-Opening Metathesis Polymerization

Continuous 3D Printing and Frontal Polymerization of a pDCPD Helix

Taken From REMAT Grant Proposal

COD/DCPD Copolymers

*Dean, *et al.* ACS Macro Lett. 2020, 9, 819-824.

Problems with Spontaneous Polymerization

COD

DCPD

Monomer(s)	Energy Density	Stability
Cyclooctadiene (COD)	7.4 kcals/mol	Prone to Spontaneous FROMP
Dicyclopentadiene (DCPD)	27.2 kcals/mol	Stable against Spontaneous FROMP
COD/DCPD Copolymers	Mixed	Prone to Spontaneous FROMP

Why do COD formulations frequently SP while DCPD homopolymer formulations rarely do?

Polymerization of DCPD

Chain 1 Coordinates to Secondary Ring π Electrons on Chain 2

Secondary Ring-Opening Initiates

Chains Continue to Propagate with DCPD Monomers

Note that the backbone double bonds are inaccessible to catalyst because of the steric blocking effect imposed by DCPD's secondary ring!

COD Polymerization

Chain 1 Coordinates to Secondary Ring π Electrons on Chain 2

Linear Metathesis Initiates

Chain 2 acts as “Chain Transfer Agent” and Chains Split!

Free Chain End Excluded Volume

x = previous crosslinking point

Strategies to Limit Spontaneous Polymerization

- **Shorter Primary Chains**

- **Lowered Temperatures**

- **Fewer Transfer Sites**

- **“Shackled” Chains**

COD

$$V \approx 146 \text{ nm}^3$$

$$V = \langle R^2 \rangle^{3/2}$$

Shackling Chains

Shackling Chains

Shear-Thinning Organogel

**Freely-Jointed
Chain Length**

**Graft
Density**

**DP between
DCPD Crosslinks**

$$V = \left(n_f l^2 \right)^{3/2}, \quad n_f = \begin{cases} n_g, & n_g < n_{Dx} \\ n_{Dx}, & n_g > n_{Dx} \end{cases}$$

Shackling Chains

Shear-Thinning Organogel

Freely-Jointed Chain Length **Graft Density** **DP between DCPD Crosslinks**

$$V = \left(n_f l^2 \right)^{3/2}, \quad n_f = \begin{cases} n_g, & n_g < n_{Dx} \\ n_{Dx}, & n_g > n_{Dx} \end{cases}$$

Extension to COD Inks

“Shackled” Chains

~60 Min Pot Life

Fewer Transfer Sites

~60 Min Pot Life

Acknowledgments

Questions?

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